

THE IMPORTANCE AND INTEGRATION OF LISTENING AND SPEAKING SKILLS IN TEACHING ENGLISH AS A FOREIGN LANGUAGE

¹Pardayeva Aziza, ²Karimova Nigina

¹Teacher of Samarkand state institute of foreign languages

²Teacher of Samarkand state institute of foreign languages

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Abstract. *In teaching English as a foreign language, the integration of listening and speaking skills plays a crucial role in effective language acquisition and communication. Listening and speaking skills are not only fundamental components of oral communication but also essential for comprehension, expression, and overall language proficiency. The importance of integrating listening and speaking skills lies in their reciprocal relationship. Listening skills provide learners with exposure to authentic language input, helping them build vocabulary, understand grammar, and develop a sense of natural pronunciation and intonation. By actively engaging in listening activities, learners can enhance their comprehension skills, identify contextual cues, and develop the ability to extract meaning from spoken language.*

Keywords: *communicative competence, framework, pronunciation, ESL/EFL.*

Teachers should teach speaking and listening in an interactive way because these two skills are always interwoven in real life. For the majority of the cases because these abilities are not utilized in integration, students may be able to talk and listen in the language but still be unable to communicate.

Dell Hymes (1971) defined communicative competence as a linguistic term that refers to a language user's grammatical knowledge, such as syntax, morphology, and phonology, as well as social knowledge about how and when to use speech appropriately. In this process, communicative competence is the way speakers of a language describe what they know, and this enables them to interact effectively with others. Therefore, teachers should place more emphasis on teaching integration skills to facilitate individual communication skills. Speaking and listening skills are considered too difficult to master, so students are usually reluctant to undertake assignments that focus on these two skills. Consolidating information gap tasks can motivate students to see real-world results and practice to better communicate their ideas. Some teachers do not like tasks with information gaps, believing that the class can get out of control and impede the communication process. Teachers must push boundaries, create a safe and stress-free environment, encourage and motivate students to speak up. An information gap task is one in which learners lack the necessary information to complete the task and need to hear and speak to each other to complete the task as they would in real life. Information gap tasks are beneficial in a foreign language environment for a number of reasons. First and foremost, both emphasize real-world communication as it enhances the opportunity to practice speaking. Students are highly motivated. One of the challenges teachers face in the classroom is motivating students to speak the target language. Active and confident students will always participate, while insecure students will not speak up. As Lightbown and Spada (2006) suggest, speaking in a target language involves multiple mental tasks at once, such as selecting words, pronouncing them, and arranging them into appropriate grammatical symbols.

is required (p. 39). Performing these manipulations during communication requires complex and involuntary mental processes, and failure to do so can lead to resistance, uncertainty, fear, and even panic, just like listening. Teachers should be classroom facilitators to create a safe environment (Jones, 2004, p. 34). Therefore, another important feature of tasks with information gaps is that each student only has a portion of the information needed to solve the task, so they can cooperate and share information by talking and listening to each other that is what you need to share. In this framework, during the learning process, students not only converse with the teacher, but also with each other. This allows all students to participate in assignments while promoting student-centered learning in the classroom. In real life, listening and speaking are always integrated, so teachers need to teach her these two skills interactively. Students may know how to listen and speak in the language, but may not be able to communicate in this language, mainly because these skills are not used for integration. Of course, using authentic materials and real-life situations can lead to skill integration. Because that's what happens in the real world. The purpose of this study is to prove that listening and speaking, both during the classroom practice phase and in real-life communicative situations, offer unique qualities that make a real contribution to overall language learning that's the teacher's job.

Understand and utilize how listening is closely related to speaking and how listening and speaking can be integrated through information gap tasks. This study presents an academic perspective, focusing on the teaching of comprehensive listening and speaking through information gap tasks. Encourage conversations in English in this way, English becomes a true means of communication and exchange between people. In addition, teachers can diversify their lessons due to the wider range of assignments. True success in teaching and learning English is when learners are able to actually communicate in English inside and outside the classroom (Davies and Pearse, 2000, p. 99). Against this background, this study aims to answer the question whether integrated teaching of listening and speaking skills improves students' oral communication skills. One of the images for teaching English as a second or foreign language (ESL/EFL) is that of a tapestry. The tapestry is woven from a variety of factors, including teachers, learner characteristics, environment, and relevant languages (English, learner's and teacher's native languages, etc.). All these threads need to be interwoven in a positive way in order to produce large, strong, beautiful and colorful tapestries on the educational loom. For example, the teacher's teaching style should be adapted to the learning style of the learner, the learner should be motivated, and the environment should provide resources and values that strongly support language teaching. there is. But unless the threads are effectively woven together, the educational loom can produce something small, flimsy, ragged, and pale that is wholly unrecognizable as a tapestry. If this weaving does not occur, the strands are just separate and distinct abilities, parallel threads that do not touch, support or interact with each other. This is sometimes called the "skills separation approach". Another name for this type of education is the language-based approach, as language itself is the focus of education (language for language's sake). This approach does not focus on learning how to communicate authentically.

By looking at the teaching of individual skills, we can see the benefits of skill integration and improve the teaching of English learners. In the individual skills approach, acquisition of individual language skills such as reading and speaking is considered key to learning success, and language learning is usually separate from content learning (Mohan, 1986). This is inconsistent with the integrated way people use their language skills in normal communication, and with the

direction language education professionals are heading in recent years. The separation of skills is reflected in her traditional ESL/EFL program, which offers courses that focus on individualized language skills. Why offer a course like this? Perhaps teachers and administrators find it logically easier to offer writing courses separate from speaking, or listening courses separate from reading. They may find it impossible to focus on multiple skills at once in the classroom, even if one or two of the skills could be fully developed without them. An extreme example is the grammar-translation method, which teaches students to analyze grammar and to translate (usually in writing) from one language to another. This method restricts language learning to a very narrow, no communicative range that does not prepare students to use the language in everyday life. Frequently, segregated-skill ESL/EFL classes present instruction in terms of skill-linked learning strategies: reading strategies, listening strategies, speaking strategies and writing strategies (see Peregoy & Boyle, 2001). Learning strategies are strategies that students employ, most often consciously, to improve their learning. Examples are guessing meaning based on context, breaking a sentence or word down into parts to understand the meaning, and practicing the language with someone else. Very frequently, experts demonstrate strategies as though they were linked to only one particular skill, such as reading or writing (e.g., Peregoy & Boyle, 2001). However, it can be confusing or misleading to believe that a given strategy is associated with only one specific language skill. Many strategies, such as paying selective attention, self-evaluating, asking questions, analyzing, synthesizing, planning and predicting, are applicable across skill areas (see Oxford, 1990). Common strategies help weave the skills together. Teaching students to improve their learning strategies in one skill area can often enhance performance in all language skills (Oxford, 1996). Fortunately, in many instances where an ESL or EFL course is labeled by a single skill, the segregation of language skills might be only partial or even illusory. If the teacher is creative, a course bearing a discrete-skill title might actually involve multiple, integrated skills. For example, in a course on intermediate reading, the teacher probably gives all of the directions orally in English, thus causing students to use their listening ability to understand the assignment. In this course, students might discuss their readings, thus employing speaking and listening skills and certain associated skills, such as pronunciation, syntax, and social usage. Students might be asked to summarize or analyze readings in written form, thus activating their writing skills. In a real sense, then, some courses that are labeled according to one specific skill might actually reflect an integrated-skill approach after all. The same can be said for ESL/EFL textbooks. A particular series might highlight certain skills in one book or another, but all the language skills might nevertheless be present in the tasks in each book. In this way, students have the benefit of practicing all the language skills in an integrated, natural, communicative way, even if one skill is the main focus of a given volume. In contrast to segregated-skill instruction, both actual and apparent, there are at least two forms of instruction that are clearly oriented toward integrating the skills. Two types of integrated-skill instruction are content-based language instruction and task-based instruction. An extreme example is the grammatical translation method. It teaches students to analyze grammar and translate it from one language to another (usually in writing). This method limits language learning to a very narrow communicative domain and does not prepare students to use the language in everyday life. With a distinct competence, her ESL/EFL courses often offer instructional credit in terms of skill-based learning strategies.

The basis of the internal mechanism of listening are such psychological processes as listening, attention, recognition and mixing of language means, their identification, their comprehension, antipathy, grouping, generalization, affirmation in memory, inference, that is, the reconstruction of someone else's thought and an adequate reaction to it. Therefore, the subject of listening is someone else's thought, encoded in the text and subject to recognition.[1]

Reading strategies, listening strategies, speaking strategies, and writing strategies (see Peregoy and Boyle, 2001). A learning strategy is a strategy that students usually consciously use to improve their learning. Examples include inferring meaning based on context, breaking sentences or words into parts to understand meaning, and practicing the language with others. Very often, experts demonstrate strategies as if they were only associated with a particular skill, such as reading and writing (Peregoy and Boyle, 2001). However, it can be confusing and misleading to think that certain strategies are only associated with certain language abilities. Many strategies such as selective attention, self-assessment, questioning, analysis, synthesis, planning, and anticipation are applicable to all skill areas (see Oxford, 1990). Shared strategies help connect skills together. Teaching students to improve their learning strategies in one skill area often improves their performance in all language skills (Oxford, 1996). Fortunately, in many cases where an ESL or EFL course is characterized by her one skill, the separation of language skills can be partial or even illusory. In fact, if teachers are creative, they can include some built-in skills in courses titled Individualized Skills. For example, in an advanced reading class, the teacher is likely to give all instructions orally in English, requiring students to use their hearing to understand the assignment. This course allows students to discuss their reading and apply speaking and listening skills, as well as specific related skills such as pronunciation, syntax and social use. Students may be asked to write a summary or analysis of what they have read to activate their writing skills. In the truest sense of the word, some courses labeled according to specific skills may actually reflect an integrative approach to competencies. The same is true for ESL/EFL textbooks. Certain series may emphasize certain skills in one book or another. This approach allows teachers to track student progress in multiple skills at once. The integration of linguistic skills facilitates not only the analysis of linguistic forms, but also the learning of real-world content. Finally, the integrated competence approach, whether content-based, task-based, or hybrid, can be highly motivating for students of all ages and backgrounds. To incorporate language skills into her ESL/EFL lessons, the teacher should consider the following steps.

- Learn about different ways of incorporating language skills into the classroom, including content-based, task-based, or a combination.

- Review your current approach and assess how well your skills are integrated. - Select materials, textbooks and technologies that promote the integration of listening, reading, speaking, writing and related skills such as syntax and vocabulary.

- Keep in mind that even if a particular course is identified with only one of her competencies, it is possible to integrate other language competencies through appropriate assignments.

- Teach language learning strategies and emphasize that certain strategies often improve performance in multiple skills.

Lack of motivation to study is observed among a large number of students. This should be taken seriously by all stakeholders: administrators, educators, policy makers in the field of education, teachers, parents and the whole society. Everyone should take steps to find out the

causes of this problem. It is necessary to conduct research to identify the pitfalls of the entire system of education in relation to the personality-oriented approach.[2]

People listen and speak in order to receive presented information or to gain knowledge about presented content. Develop one's own intellectual capacity and be able to express ideas more concretely, intelligently over facts effectively manipulated, perhaps to influence the actions of others or determine their consequences A series of operations. These reasons for listening and speaking are fundamentally practical. So, you can say Listening serves many purposes other than listening to the language itself. A student who speaks a foreign language shouldn't worry too much about it in order to be able to do something else. Language to communicate in sent messages. Therefore, students not only develop their listening skills, but also speech skills for communicating with others. For a while, it was common in language education to teach speaking as a primary school class. Important, but less important is listening, but it is known that oral and auditory skills cannot be improved and separated from each other. Language teachers should encourage students to make predictions, tolerate ambiguity, and make connections. This eliminates the need to deal with isolated words that are not important for understanding, facilitate communication. Teachers can also help students develop their competencies by pre-discussing titles, subjects, and cultural contexts. When choosing a task, you can use all kinds of materials - from advertising to literature. In First Language, students have easy access to language used in meaningful contexts and integrate what they need. Transfer the patterns of these models into your own changing and evolving linguistic system. What they often lack is teaching a second language provides an opportunity to develop a sufficient linguistic foundation upon which to build the language. What is the message they want to convey? It is effective to use easy-to-understand materials in the classroom problem. Therefore, all tasks should function to facilitate communicative acquisition of other language skills. Including listening and speaking. Students can speak at a much higher level. Inside the system of this think about, it was realized that the understudies were willing to take an interest within the errands as the two abilities were displayed in integration through information-gap assignments, which created real life circumstances within the classroom. Tuning in could be an open aptitude in that the audience is accepting a message from a speaker, but it shouldn't cruel that the listener is inactive amid a tuning in errand. The listening process, in a way, could be an exceptionally dynamic prepare as the audience has to utilize foundation information to get it the aiming message of the speaker; so, the audience members ought to bargain with different assignments whereas tuning in to actuate their schemata. The follow-up of these stages can effortlessly be the generation organize, which unavoidably implies the integration of aptitudes. Thus, instructing the abilities independently will impact contrarily the communication within the classroom; subsequently, the instructors ought to make genuine life circumstances not as it were by joining tuning in and talking abilities but moreover by actualizing information-gap errands to improve genuine communication among the people.

In conclusion, it is seen that the comes about of the test appear that students' victory increments when these two aptitudes are instructed in integration through information-gap assignments. In addition, practicing the abilities through information gap errands carry up student involvement and inspiration primarily since these sorts of errands are related to genuine life and hence leads to communication. It may be said that the listening and talking abilities are at slightest as critical as the perusing and composing abilities. This think about proposes that students' victory rises when tuning in and talking aptitudes are coordinates through information-gap tasks. This

article has been made as a direct for instructors of English as an outside dialect to create the understudies' capacities within the dialect. It is the application of a joining approach for the development of communicative abilities within the classroom, in which the four abilities in the acquisition of information of a remote dialect can be taught in a coherent way, and practiced in, conjunction with a qualification of the significance of one upon the others. With cautious reflection and arranging, any educator can coordinate the dialect aptitudes and fortify the embroidered artwork of dialect educating and learning. When the embroidered artwork is woven well, learners can utilize English successfully for communication.

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